

FORMATION OF COTTON GAINING INDUSTRY OF SURKHAN OASIS AND ITS PLACE IN ECONOMIC LIFE

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to the history of the emergence of the cotton ginning industry in the southern Surkhan oasis of our country, and the history of these enterprises. Mainly, the establishment of cotton ginning factories in the oasis and their role in economic life were analyzed based on scientific sources.*

Keywords: *Surkhan oasis, Second World War, Termiz cotton factory, Denov cotton factory, Sherabad cotton factory, industrial enterprises, economy.*

INTRODUCTION

After the Russian Empire fully established its power in the region and took control of all aspects of social and economic life, it began to prepare the territory of Central Asia for the production of various raw materials in accordance with its geographical capabilities. As a result of the organized expeditions, geological, geographical, hydrographic and other types of economic maps of the Central Asian region were created, and the work of using each region as much as possible began. In addition to the identified mineral resources, the potential for the production of agricultural products was also highly evaluated. As a result, from the end of the 19th century, the empire became increasingly interested in growing cotton as the main industrial product.

It is known that cotton was one of the most important industrial products of the 18 th-19th centuries, and it was used to make not only yarn, cotton, fabric, but also artificial fiber, film, varnish and about 300 other products[1]. It is noteworthy that during the imperial period, cotton cultivation was carried out mainly at the agricultural level, and the product was transported to the center by means of newly completed trains. Cotton processing is almost non-existent in Central Asia, and the construction of industrial enterprises for this purpose has been carried out very slowly. For example, before the revolution of the Russian Empire in 1917, only 1.5-2% of the industrial cotton produced in factories was processed in Central Asia[2]. It is clear from this that the empire did not aim to develop the industry of this region using the territories under its control only as a supplier of products.

For this reason, industrial production in the territory of Central Asia was carried out mainly in the form of small craft enterprises. The first steam-powered cotton gin in Turkestan was built in 1874 in Tashkent[3]. The first industrial type cotton gin was built in 1881 in Tashkent, where 2 wooden gins with brushes worked. In this industrial enterprise, almost all work was done by hand, only seeding and press fertilization were done with the help of machines[4].

As a result of the acceleration of cotton planting in the southern regions of Uzbekistan, there is a need to build a cotton ginning plant in this region. Among them, the cotton factory of the Matchinboyev brothers, which started its activity, is one of the first.

In 1905, the Matchinboyev brothers, intending to build a cotton gin, went on a trip to St. Petersburg, where they met with Russian engineers. From there, he brings six gin machines for processing cotton and hires specialists who operate them. Construction of the plant started in 1906. The construction of the plant will take longer than planned. Because there was a lack of specialists

who could lead the construction and commissioning of the plant. In order to prevent this situation, the Matchinboyevs began to gather around them qualified specialists. As a result, the construction work was revived in 1909, and the cotton gin started producing products for the first time in 1910[5]. This cotton gin is the first and only enterprise of its kind in Surkhandarya, the main factories are located in other regions of the Bukhara Emirate and there are 26 of them. Thus, in 1910, the first industrial enterprise in the center of the oasis, Termiz, began to produce products. One of the first industrial enterprises established in Termiz region is A. Ananov's cotton factory. In the territory of Central Asia, American cotton varieties began to be grown at the end of the 19th century, and in 1907, the American "Upland" variety was planted instead of local cotton in the Surkhandarya region[6]. Planting American varieties was considered more profitable than planting other types of crops. Because the annual increase in the amount of duty charged by the Russian Empire on cotton imported from America increased the demand of local farmers for cotton and raised the price of local products[7]. caused an increase due to their interests.

METHODS

In the article, based on the principles of objectivity, historical analysis, comparative-logical analysis, chronological sequence, the formation of cotton ginning enterprises and their role in the economic life of the Surkhan oasis are explained based on scientific sources.

RESULTS

In the development of the cotton industry in the southern regions of Uzbekistan, representatives of the local self-sufficient population also have their place. Because in Central Asia, before the construction of the Soviet power and the workers' country based on socialism, beneficial relations were established with the Russian Empire and some representatives of the local people. Through this, the empire would get the raw materials it needed, and representatives of the local population would organize this process. One of the representatives who took an active part in the development of cotton farming and the opening of a cotton factory in the southern region was Abduvosi Halimov, originally from Tashkent, who in history showed enthusiasm in the construction of the Abduvosiboy cotton factory. After the construction of the railway, Abduvosi Halimov will make good use of it in trade. Realizing that it is more profitable to sell fiber than cotton, Abduvosi Halimov builds a cotton ginning plant. But due to the coup d'état in 1917 and the coming of the Soviets to power, the Council of Worker-Soldier Deputies was elected in Termiz under the chairmanship of Preobrazhensky. This government, which has been against the rich and nobles since the beginning of its activity, forms lists of representatives of the local population. In this situation, Abduvosi Halimov transferred all the enterprises and factories owned by him to the Soviets, and as a result, his cotton factory was later included in the current Termiz cotton ginning plant.

If we compare the first factories of the cotton industry established in the oasis, the cotton factories of Abduvosi Halimov and A. Ananov were not bigger than the factory of Matchinboev. Matchinboev's cotton ginning factory was equipped with the simplest equipment, and the installed machines were set in motion by burning reeds and rings. Most of the production process was done by hand. For this reason, the workers transported the cotton themselves and pressed the resulting fibers by hand in simple presses. On average, 20-25 bales of cotton were produced at the factory per day, and the weight of each bale was 60-70 kilograms. That is, on average 1200-1800 kilograms of fiber were produced per day. 1200-1800 kilograms of fiber were produced per year.

After the October Revolution of 1917, representatives of the government, consisting of workers, soldiers, and peasants, came to the top of the government. When the Soviet representatives, who planned to build a state without mutual equality and private ownership, without the rich, took full control over the territories of the former Russian Empire, they continued the same works of the empire. Attention has been paid to the development of cotton growing and related industries in Central Asia, in particular in the Turkestan ASSR, the USSR and the USSR.

However, between 1917 and 1920, it cannot be said that the cotton industry developed rapidly neither in the Surkhan oasis nor in other regions. Because the defeat in the First World War and a large amount of reparations, the civil war, the harsh policy carried out by the Soviets in agriculture made the life of the population in the country difficult, the peasants became despondent, hunger increased, and agricultural products became scarce. As a result, industrial activity remained at a very low level at this time. Along with the development of the cotton industry, the establishment of other handicraft associations in the country had a positive effect on the industry and economy of the regions. Surkhandarya is not far behind in this regard. In the 20s of the 20th century, there were 12,278 craft enterprises in Turkestan, of which 1,728 (14%) were located in Surkhandarya[8]. In 1927-1928, all industrial enterprises of Surkhandarya, together with the cotton industry, produced products worth 2 million 72 thousand soums, handicraft enterprises produced products worth 3 million 884 thousand soums[9]. It can be seen that at the end of the 20s of the 20th century, industrial enterprises were not in the leading position in the economy of Surkhandarya, but only in the second half of the 30s, as a result of the construction and modernization of new cotton gins, the industry gained an important place in the country's economy. This was supported by the promotion of various social movements by the Soviets, in particular, "Stakhanovism" and other movements in cotton factories. Intensification of mass movements, entry of women workers into the industry, modernization of old equipment lead to industrial development. On November 1, 1921, after the establishment of the Turkestan Cotton Committee, the Termiz cotton ginning plant was taken over by the state and transferred to this committee. The goal was to centralize all processes related to cotton growing. In 1923, the Bukhara and Khorezm cotton committees separated from the Turkestan cotton committee. In 1925, Uzbek ("Uzbekhlopkom"), Turkmen, and Kazakh cotton committees separated from the Turkistan Cotton Committee[10]. The partition of 1925 was connected with the national territorial delimitation of Central Asia in 1924, and separate committees were established for the new Soviet republics. As a result, 1925 tons of cotton was grown in 1924, 6252 tons in 1927, and 15150 tons in 1928[8]. As a result of this, the work of the existing cotton ginning plant, as well as the activity of new enterprises, was formed. This led to the recovery of the economy of the oasis, albeit slowly.

DISCUSSION

In particular, the Termiz cotton ginning plant was equipped with new press machines in 1926-1927. In 1927, in the city of Termiz, two 450-horsepower diesel engines were installed and a power station was established. However, the main work in the factory was still done by manual labor.

In 1925, despite the fact that there were 21 sectors in the industry of Uzbekistan, the state had an agrarian-industrial economy. At that time, the share of agriculture was equal to 61.8%[11]. For this reason, plans for the implementation of the industrialization policy in the entire Union began to be drawn up. The industrialization of each allied republic was carried out in accordance

with its historical and natural conditions. Therefore, it was planned to implement the process of industrialization in the Uzbek SSR with an emphasis on agriculture, especially the cotton industry.

In 1939-1940, the Termiz cotton ginning plant was reconstructed. 1291.5 thousand soums were spent on this work. In 1939, a new type of power station building was put into operation at the plant. The commissioning of this power plant significantly improved the plant's electricity needs. Smooth operation of machinery and equipment was ensured. The plant has been equipped with new advanced equipment. In order to improve the production process of the plant, in 1940, a modern engine with a capacity of 400 horsepower was installed.

By 1945, the remaining 12 gins from the 2nd ginning plant were sent to the Mari cotton ginning plant. The indicators of the Termiz cotton ginning plant in the 30 years after its operation have been constantly growing. For the fact that the employees of the factory exceeded the plans of 1943 and achieved high indicators, the factory was awarded the Portable Red Flag of the People's Commissariat of the Textile Industry of the UzSSR and the Association of Cotton Ginneries of the Central Committee of the USSR and a cash prize of 10,000 soum. The equipment of cotton ginning factories processing cotton with new machinery and equipment was continued. In 1946, the Termiz cotton ginning plant was reconstructed. Instead of the old type of 6 pcs. 70 saws, modern 4 pcs. brushless GSM-3 pcs. A gin machine with 70 saws was installed at the plant in 1945, and a gin machine with 80 saws was installed in 1946. The built-in 80 saw gin machine had its advantages. If in 1945 the fiber-separating machines separated 520-560 kg of fiber per hour, with the help of new machines, it was possible to separate 2200-2400 kg of fiber per hour. In 1948, instead of 7,500 tons of fiber, 7,666 tons of fiber were produced. 111.3% of the 1949 plan was fulfilled and 8,595 tons of fiber, 200 tons of wool, and 13,582 tons of seeds were produced.

CONCLUSION

In Surkhandarya region, under the leadership of Termiz cotton ginning plant, other factories of smaller capacity were established. In order to ensure the continuous operation of these factories, many other related sectors were created by the union: Machine tractor stations (MTS), power plants, educational and research institutes, railway stations, housing, communal services center, hospitals and schools, as well as all necessary conditions for efficient collection of cotton and sending it to the processing center were created. Of course, as a result of this, the socio-economic conditions of Surkhandarya improved, the number of workers increased, the infrastructure serving the population was built, water stations were built, and new lands were developed. However, all these changes were carried out in order to destroy local customs and traditions that have been preserved for centuries, to convince the population of the ideology of socialism, and in fact to provide the center with the necessary products.

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